

CORONAVIRUS COVID-19: AVAILABLE FREE LITERATURE PROVIDED BY VARIOUS COMPANIES, JOURNALS AND ORGANIZATIONS AROUND THE WORLD

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Encouraging Young Chemists

A tidy laboratory means a lazy chemist.
-- Jöns Jacob Berzelius (Swedish chemist, 1779-1848)

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Coronavirus COVID-19: Available Free Literature Provided by Various Companies, Journals and Organizations around the World

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Abstract

Human history is observing a very strange time fighting an invisible enemy; the novel COVID-19 coronavirus. Initially observed in the Wuhan province of China, now fastly spreading around the world. Various journals are offering to freely publish the articles about Coronavirus. As this pandemic is very new and very less scientific material is available on the topic, various paid journals and companies are offering free materials published about the Coronavirus. Here in this short review, we will discuss the articles about Coronavirus that are freely provided by various journals and companies around the world. This review is open to updates. If you find some more free resources available, let us know at info@scimatic.org to update.

Keywords: Coronavirus, Pandemic, Covid-19, Free Articles, Articles About Coronavirus

COVID-19, the novel pandemic

Mankind has observed various pandemics throughout the history where some of the were more disastrous than the others to the humans. We are observing a very tough time once again fighting an invisible enemy; the novel COVID-19 coronavirus. Initially observed in the Wuhan province of China, now fastly spreading around the world.

As of today, 20th March, 2020, there are 270,069 Coronavirus cases, with 11,271 deaths while 90,603 has been recovered. In the total Coronavirus patients died, very interestingly the highest number belongs to Italy i.e. 4,032 deaths. The death toll is followed by China (3,248), Iran (1,433) and Spain (1,044) [<https://www.worldometers.info/coronavirus/>].

Figure 1. The rise of deaths and active cases of Coronavirus

Various journals are offering to publish your articles for free about Coronavirus. Here in this short review, we will discuss the articles about Coronavirus that are freely provided by various journals and companies.

American Chemical Society (ACS)

ACS is providing various articles published in the *ACS Infectious Diseases*, *ACS Chemical Biology*, *Journal of Medicinal Chemistry*, *Biochemistry*, *Chemical Reviews*, and *ACS Applied Materials & Interfaces* as well as the preprint server ChemRxiv. These articles can be accessed from the link below:

https://pubs.acs.org/page/vi/chemistry_coronavirus_research?utm_source=pubs_content_marketing&utm_medium=email&utm_campaign=0320_MFH_PUBS_0320_MFH_CoronavirusSecondEmail&ref=pubs_content_marketing

These articles are explained in the below lines.

Characterizing virus structure and mechanism of infection

1. Multiplex Paper-Based Colorimetric DNA Sensor Using PyrrolidinyI Peptide Nucleic Acid-Induced AgNPs Aggregation for Detecting MERS-CoV, MTB, and HPV Oligonucleotides [Teengam et al, 2017]
2. Evidence of the COVID-19 Virus Targeting the CNS: Tissue Distribution, Host-Virus Interaction, and Proposed Neurotropic Mechanisms [Baig et al, 2020]
3. Research and Development on Therapeutic Agents and

- Vaccines for COVID-19 and Related Human Coronavirus Diseases [Liu et al, 2020]
4. Putative Receptor Binding Domain of Bat-Derived Coronavirus HKU9 Spike Protein: Evolution of Betacoronavirus Receptor Binding Motifs [Huang et al, 2016]
 5. Inhibiting APOBEC3 Activity with Single-Stranded DNA Containing 2'-Deoxyzebularine Analogues [Kvach, 2019]
 6. Inhibitor Recognition Specificity of MERS-CoV Papain-like Protease May Differ from That of SARS-CoV [Lee et al, 2015]
 7. Enzyme-Catalyzed Kinetic Resolution of Chiral Precursors to Antiviral Prodrugs [Xiang et al, 2019]
 8. Immunodominant SARS Coronavirus Epitopes in Humans Elicited both Enhancing and Neutralizing Effects on Infection in Non-human Primates [Wang et al, 2016]
 9. Functional Carbon Quantum Dots as Medical Countermeasures to Human Coronavirus [oczechin et al, 2019]
 10. Single-Virus Tracking: From Imaging Methodologies to Virological Applications [Liu et al, 2020]
 11. Homology Models of Coronavirus 3CLpro Protease [Stoermer, 2020]

Development of treatment approaches

1. Broad Spectrum Antiviral Agent Niclosamide and Its Therapeutic Potential [Xu et al, 2020]
2. Structure-Based Stabilization of Non-native Protein-Protein Interactions of Coronavirus Nucleocapsid Proteins in Antiviral Drug Design [Lin et al, 2020]
3. α -Ketoamides as Broad-Spectrum Inhibitors of Coronavirus and Enterovirus Replication: Structure-Based Design, Synthesis, and Activity Assessment [Zhang, 2020]
4. Integration of Global Analyses of Host Molecular Responses with Clinical Data To Evaluate Pathogenesis and Advance Therapies for Emerging and Re-emerging Viral Infections [Falcinelli et al, 2016]
5. An Overview of Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome-Coronavirus (SARS-CoV) 3CL Protease Inhibitors: Peptidomimetics and Small Molecule Chemotherapy [Pillaiyar et al, 2016]
6. Discovery of Hydrocarbon-Stapled Short α -Helical Peptides as Promising Middle East Respiratory Syndrome Coronavirus (MERS-CoV) Fusion Inhibitors [Wang, 2018]
7. Design, Synthesis, and Anti-RNA Virus Activity of 6'-Fluorinated-Aristeromycin Analogues [Yoon, 2019]
8. De Novo Design of α -Helical Lipopeptides Targeting Viral Fusion Proteins: A Promising Strategy for Relatively Broad-Spectrum Antiviral Drug Discovery [Wang, 2018]
9. Combating Intracellular Pathogens with Repurposed Host-Targeted Drugs [Schor et al, 2018]
10. Peptide-Based Vaccines: Current Progress and Future Challenges [Malonis et al, 2019]
11. The ProTide Prodrug Technology: From the Concept to the Clinic [Mehellou et al, 2018]
12. Cell-Membrane-Mimicking Nanodecoys against Infectious Diseases [Rao et al, 2020]
13. Learning from the Past: Possible Urgent Prevention and Treatment Options for Severe Acute Respiratory Infections Caused by 2019-nCoV [Morse et al, 2020]

SciMatic

SciMatic (<https://scimatic.org>) is offering to publish articles free of cost related to the Coronavirus. Journal of Ongoing Chemical Research

(<https://scimatic.org/journals/1>) will not charge the writers for articles on the Coronavirus related topics. In addition, the SciMatic literature manager (<https://scimatic.org>) can be used freely to search published literature among more than 21,000 journals being indexed.

Semantic Scholar

Semantic Scholar has already announced COVID-19 Open Research Dataset (<https://pages.semanticscholar.org/coronavirus-research>).

In response to the COVID-19 pandemic, the [Allen Institute for AI](#) has partnered with leading research groups to prepare and distribute the COVID-19 Open Research Dataset (CORD-19), a free resource of over 44,000 scholarly articles, including over 29,000 with full text, about COVID-19 and the coronavirus family of viruses for use by the global research community.

This dataset is intended to mobilize researchers to apply recent advances in natural language processing to generate new insights in support of the fight against this infectious disease. The corpus will be updated weekly as new research is published in peer-reviewed publications and archival services like [bioRxiv](#), [medRxiv](#), and others.

Resources provided by the Allen Institute for Artificial Intelligence

- [SciSpacy](#), a text processing toolkit optimized for scientific text (<https://allenai.github.io/scispacy/>)
- [SciBERT](#), a BERT model pretrained on scientific text (<https://github.com/allenai/scibert>)
- [Semantic Scholar API](#) (<http://s2-public-api-prod.us-west-2.elasticbeanstalk.com/>) and [Open Research Corpus](#) (<http://s2-public-api-prod.us-west-2.elasticbeanstalk.com/corpus/>)
- Create an AI-powered customizable [adaptive feed of COVID-19 research](#) (<https://www.semanticscholar.org/feed/create?name=COVID-19&paperIds=4adf89030bb59f9cd97a55af21b419aad9045287%2C272c530d8b3a2daae3af01fa4a59b350f3a5398b%2Ca42902bc3f4d92b72f46775420be6569d19e3f73>)

World Health Organization (WHO)

WHO is gathering the latest scientific findings and knowledge on coronavirus disease (COVID-19) and compiling it in a database. We update the database daily from searches of bibliographic databases, hand searches of the table of contents of relevant journals, and the addition of other relevant scientific articles that come to our attention. The entries in the database may

not be exhaustive and new research will be added regularly. A full database can be downloaded at <https://www.who.int/emergencies/diseases/novel-coronavirus-2019/global-research-on-novel-coronavirus-2019-ncov>.

TheBMJ

BMJ is providing latest news and resources about Coronavirus (covid-19) at <https://www.bmj.com/coronavirus> including the latest coverage from The BMJ Editorials, news, opinions, most read articles about Coronavirus.

Articles from the BMJ's specialty journals

- [Heart](#)—[Cardiologists and Coronavirus](#): Looking after ourselves and each other so we can continue to look after patients
- [BMJ Simulation & Technology Enhanced Learning](#)—Preparing and responding to 2019 novel coronavirus with simulation and technology-enhanced learning for healthcare professionals
- [BMJ Open Respiratory Research](#)—Effect of acute respiratory infections in infancy on pulmonary function test at 3 years of age
- [General Psychiatry](#)—A nationwide survey of psychological distress among Chinese people in the COVID-19 epidemic
- [BMJ Open](#)—Influence of trust on two different risk perceptions as an affective and cognitive dimension during Middle East respiratory syndrome coronavirus (MERS-CoV) outbreak in South Korea
- [British Journal of Ophthalmology](#)—The importance of recognising possible early ocular manifestation and using protective eyewear
- [European Journal of Hospital Pharmacy](#)—Houston we have a problem: coronavirus
- [Gut](#)—SARS-CoV-2 induced diarrhoea as onset symptom in patient with COVID-19
- [Gut](#)—Diarrhoea may be underestimated: a missing link in 2019 novel coronavirus
- [BMJ Global Health](#)—An updated roadmap for MERS-CoV research and product development
- [Family Medicine and Community Health](#)—Challenges and responsibilities of family doctors in the new global coronavirus outbreak
- [Family Medicine and Community Health](#)—Preparedness of community-based organisations in biohazard

Additionally, BMJ also provides BMJ's clinical decision support tool and Interactive, peer reviewed learning modules from BMJ.

Cambridge University Press

Cambridge University Press has started a Coronavirus Free Access Collection at <https://www.cambridge.org/core/browse-subjects/medicine/coronavirus-free-access-collection>. They have

133 articles on 21st March, 2020.

Centers for Disease Control and Prevention

The Center of Disease Control (CDC) and Prevention belong to the government of United States has started a separate page entitled Coronavirus (COVID-19). The page is live at <https://www.cdc.gov/coronavirus/2019-ncov/index.html>. This page provides the details about how to protect yourself, if you think you are sick, symptoms, older adults and medical conditions, prepare your family and a detailed map stating the current status of the Coronavirus in the US.

CDC is responding to a [pandemic](#) of respiratory disease [spreading](#) from person-to-person caused by a novel (new) [coronavirus](#). The disease has been named “coronavirus disease 2019” (abbreviated “COVID-19”). This situation poses a serious [public health risk](#). The federal government is working closely with state, local, tribal, and territorial partners, as well as public health partners, to [respond](#) to this situation. COVID-19 can cause [mild to severe illness](#); most severe illness occurs in older adults.

Cochrane

Cochrane has started a special Collection entitled Coronavirus (COVID-19): evidence relevant to critical care at <https://www.cochrane.org/special-collection-coronavirus-covid-19-evidence-relevant-critical-care>. Cochrane is for anyone interested in using high-quality information to make health decisions. Whether you are a doctor or nurse, patient or carer, researcher or funder, Cochrane evidence provides a powerful tool to enhance your healthcare knowledge and decision making. Cochrane has released a [Special Collection: Coronavirus \(COVID-19\): evidence relevant to critical care](#), which is also available in [Simplified Chinese](#), [Farsi](#), [French](#), [Japanese](#), [Bahasa Malaysia](#), and [Spanish](#). News item available in [German](#) and [Polish](#).

Elsevier

Elsevier has started its own Novel Coronavirus Information Center. Here you will find expert, curated information for the research and health community on novel coronavirus (COVID-19). All resources are free to access and include guidelines for clinicians and patients. There are various sections for researchers, clinicians, patients etc. The page is live at <https://www.elsevier.com/connect/coronavirus-infor>

[mation-center.](#)

European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control (ECDC)

ECDC, is an agency of the European Union, is publishing informations about the Coronavirus at <https://www.ecdc.europa.eu/en>. Another page of ECDC at <https://www.ecdc.europa.eu/en/novel-coronavirus-china> provides information about COVID-19 in addition to

- [Latest situation update, epidemiological curve and global distribution](#)
- [Situation dashboard: latest available data](#)
- [Current risk assessment](#)
- [Q&A on COVID-19](#)

In addition, this page provides detailed situation update worldwide on the map, situation update for the EU/EEA and the UK, and an interactive map situation dashboard.

JAMA Network

JAMA Network is providing informations on the Coronavirus Disease 2019 (COVID-19), updated and treatments at <https://jamanetwork.com/journals/jama/pages/coronavirus-alert>. There are various video tutorials on the page. This page is mostly informative about the COVID-19:

- [Epidemiology](#)
- [Clinical Management](#)
- [Public Health Preparedness](#)
- [Patient Information](#)
- [Multimedia](#)
- [Outbreak Map](#)
- [CDC Guidance](#)
- [WHO Guidance](#)

The Lancet

The Lancet has started a COVID-19 resource center at <https://www.thelancet.com/coronavirus>. To assist health workers and researchers working under challenging conditions to bring this outbreak to a close, *The Lancet* has created a Coronavirus Resource Centre. This resource brings together new 2019 novel coronavirus disease (COVID-19) content from across *The Lancet* journals as it is published. All of our COVID-19 content is free to access. This page provides informations about various editorials, comments, world report, correspondence, and an email for media queries.

The New England Journal of Medicine (NEJM)

NEJM is providing a collection of articles and other resources on the Coronavirus (Covid-19) outbreak, including clinical reports, management guidelines, and commentary at <https://www.nejm.org/coronavirus>. There are also many articles linked to the page with few lines of introduction.

Oxford University Press

Oxford University Press has create a page at <https://academic.oup.com/journals/pages/coronavirus?cc=us&lang=en&> about the free access to OUP resources on coronavirus and related topics. The articles are provided by the journals published by the OUP and/or related companies mainly Clinical Infectious Diseases, Open Forum Infectious Diseases, Clinical Kidney Journal, Nephrology Dialysis Transplantation, Journal of Antimicrobial Chemotherapy etc. There are also articles provided by Oxford Medicine Online.

PLOS Blogs

PLOS Blogs has started a blog on the novel coronavirus (2019-nCoV) outbreak at <https://blogs.plos.org/plos/2020/01/novel-coronavirus-2019-ncov-outbreak/>. There is also another campaign at this page where many companies has signed or promised to provide open access articles related to the Coronavirus COVID-19 at <https://wellcome.ac.uk/press-release/sharing-research-data-and-findings-relevant-novel-coronavirus-covid-19-outbreak>.

Signatories to the statement

- Academy of Medical Sciences, UK
- Africa Centres for Disease Control and Prevention (Africa CDC)
- African Academy of Sciences
- American Chemical Society (ACS)*
- American Society for Microbiology*
- Annals of Internal Medicine*
- arXiv
- Assistant Secretary for Preparedness and Response / Biodefense Advanced Research and Development Authority, USA
- Australian and New Zealand Intensive Care Society (ANZICS)
- Austrian Science Fund (FWF)
- BenevolentAI
- Bernhard Nocht Institute for Tropical Medicine (BNITM)
- Bill & Melinda Gates Foundation
- Biochemical Society & Portland Press
- BioRxiv
- Biotechnology and Biological Sciences Research Council (BBSRC), UK
- The British Medical Journal (BMJ)*

- Bulletin of the World Health Organization*
- CABI
- Calouste Gulbenkian Foundation – Gulbenkian Science Institute
- Cambridge University Press (CUP)*
- Canada Foundation for Innovation
- Canadian Institutes of Health Research
- Cell Press*
- Center for Biomedical Research Transparency (CBMRT)
- Centers for Disease Prevention and Control (CDC), USA
- CEPI
- Chinese Centre for Disease Control and Prevention
- Chinese Journal of Lung Cancer*
- Cold Spring Harbor Laboratory Press
- Department of Biotechnology, Ministry of Science & Technology, Government of India
- The Department for International Development (DFID), UK
- Dutch Research Council (NWO)
- eLife*
- EcoHealth Alliance
- Elsevier*
- EMBO
- EMBO Press*
- Emerald Publishing*
- Epicentre – MSF
- European Commission
- European Respiratory Society*
- European University Association (EUA)
- F1000 Research Limited*
- Fondation Merieux
- Food & Drug Administration, USA
- French National Research Agency (ANR)
- Frontiers*
- Future Science Group (FSG)*
- GeoVax
- The Global Health Network
- Global Virus Network
- GLOPID-R
- Healthcare Infection Society*
- Health Research Board, Ireland
- Hindawi*
- Indiana University
- Infectious Diseases Data Observatory (IDDO)
- Inserm (Institut national de la santé et de la recherche médicale), France
- Institute of Tropical Medicine, Antwerp, Belgium
- The Institut Pasteur
- International Forum for Acute Care Trialists (InFACT)
- International Severe Acute Respiratory and emerging Infection Consortium (ISARIC)
- International Society for Infectious Diseases (ISID)
- IOP Publishing*
- The JAMA Network
- Japan Agency for Medical Research and Development (AMED)
- JMIR Publications*
- Johnson & Johnson
- Kaohsiung Journal of Medical Sciences
- Karger Publishers*
- Kent Ridge Health Singapore
- The Lancet*
- Life Science Alliance*
- Luxembourg National Research Fund (FNR)
- MDPI*
- Medical Research Council (UK)
- Médecins Sans Frontières/Doctors Without Borders (MSF)
- MedRxiv
- Merck Research Laboratories
- Microbide Limited
- Microbiology Society*
- National Academy of Medicine, USA
- National Institute for Health Research (NIHR), UK
- National Institutes of Health (NIH), USA
- National Institute for Infectious Diseases Lazzaro Spallanzani, Italy
- New England Journal of Medicine (NEJM)*
- Office of Global Affairs, Department of Health and Human Services, USA
- Oxford University Press*
- Penn State University
- PLOS*
- PNAS – Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the USA*
- ProMED
- The Research Council of Norway
- Research Square
- Rockefeller University Press (RUP)*
- The Royal Society*
- SAGE Publishing*
- Science Europe
- Science Foundation Ireland
- Science Journals – American Association for the Advancement of Science*
- ScienceOpen
- Sciencepaper Online
- Society for Applied Microbiology
- South African Medical Research Council
- Springer Nature*
- SSRN
- STM
- Swedish Research Council
- Takeda
- Taylor & Francis*
- UNIMED – Mediterranean Universities Union
- Wellcome Trust
- WikiJournal User Group*
- Wiley*
- Wolters Kluwer*
- ZonMW – The Netherlands Organisation for Health Research and Development

*[These journals/publishers have also agreed](#) to make all of their COVID-19 and coronavirus-related publications, and the available data supporting them, immediately accessible in PubMed Central (PMC) and license it in ways that facilitate reuse.

Springer Nature

Springer Nature has started a page on the SARS-CoV-2 and COVID-19, A new virus and associated respiratory disease that is live at <https://www.springernature.com/gp/researchers/campaigns/coronavirus>.

Springer Nature is providing research articles from their journals, as well as additional commentary on this topic and relevant books. All content listed here is free to access. Please contact our [customer services team](#) if the literature is not available for free.

Springer Nature encourages [early sharing of](#)

[research](#) submitted to all our journals through preprints, and their [In Review](#) preprint service is available for many journals. They strongly urge authors submitting articles related to this emergency to [share underlying datasets relating to the outbreak](#) as rapidly and widely as possible.

Springer Nature also continue to work with global organisations to support the sharing of relevant research and data, including supporting the [World Health Organisation](#) and the initiative from the [White House Office of Science and Technology](#) to make all relevant global research, and data, immediately available in [one place](#) via PubMed Central. They are also a signatory on the consensus statement, [Sharing research data and findings relevant to the novel coronavirus \(COVID-19\) outbreak](#).

SSRN (Preprints)

SSRN Coronavirus page is live at <https://www.ssrn.com/index.cfm/en/coronavirus/>. SSRN's Coronavirus and Infectious Disease Research page provides a curated view into the early-stage research to help researchers, public health authorities, clinicians and the public understand, contain and manage this disease.

Rapidly evolving healthcare emergencies necessitate the quick dissemination of research. The growing role of early-stage research, often referred to as preprints, was acknowledged in the Ebola and Zika virus outbreaks as a way of "[accelerating the dissemination of scientific findings to support responses to infectious disease outbreaks](#)". SSRN, Elsevier's world-leading platform devoted to the rapid worldwide dissemination of early-stage research, is committed to making coronavirus-related research available immediately. Research on SSRN is free to download and upload. It is important to note that these papers have not benefited from the pivotal role of peer-review, which validates and improves the quality of final published journal articles.

Content is presented in the following categories:

- [COVID-19 Research](#) - on the COVID-19 outbreak originating in Wuhan, Hubei province, China, and escalating in January 2020
- [Infectious Disease Research](#) - on infectious diseases including coronavirus, SARS, MERS and Ebola
- [Interdisciplinary Coronavirus & Infectious Disease Related Research](#) - related to public health, legal, economic, societal and fiscal implications

A few additional resources for staying up to date on COVID-19

- The Johns Hopkins [Coronavirus COVID-19 Global Cases site](#)
- The US CDC's [Coronavirus disease 2019 \(COVID-19\) web page](#)
- Healthmap animated view of the [spread of COVID-19](#)

Wiley

Wiley's page on Covid-19: Novel Coronavirus Outbreak is active at <https://novel-coronavirus.onlinelibrary.wiley.com>.

In addition to the articles on this site related to the current outbreak, Wiley is also making a collection of [journal articles](#) and our [book chapters](#) on coronavirus research freely available to the global scientific community. *On workdays, newly published articles are made free within 24 hours of publication. Articles published after 14:00 (EST) on Friday will be made free the following Monday.*

In response to the call to action from OSTP and other governments, Wiley will start feeding content into PubMed Central as it comes in and licensing it to maximize discoverability and usability.

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